
A comparison of photovoltaic sun tracking methods

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Abstract: Solar energy is one of the cleanest and most sustainable sources of energy that many countries are investing in. Photovoltaic panels are becoming increasingly popular due to their renewable energy perspective and low environmental impact. However, their efficiency is limited by the fixed position of the panels, which results in a reduced amount of solar radiation being captured during the day. Solar tracking systems are gaining ground as they propose to optimize the angle of incidence of the sun's rays on photovoltaic panels to address the low efficiency issue of fixed PV panels.

This study compares different methods of solar tracking systems with single-axis PV panels to quantify the increase in energy production versus fixed PV panels. A simple sun tracking method based on the sun-path diagram is compared with more advanced approaches using the incident angle of the sun ray, measured by a sun position sensor. The electric output power produced by the photovoltaic system can also be used to track the sun's position with a high degree of accuracy. Other hybrid strategies combining different sun tracking algorithms are also proposed to improve the low PV efficiency during cloudy days.

The performance of the solar tracking system is evaluated by measuring the power output of the PV panels in both static and dynamic positions. A test bench of several PV panels is used to compare the performance of the different sun trackers simultaneously, under the same weather conditions. Key parameters such as solar radiation, sun position in the sky and generated output voltage and current are considered to evaluate the effectiveness of the various sun tracking methods.

Keywords: Solar Energy, Sun Tracking System, Sun Sensor, Single-axis Photovoltaic Panel

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar photovoltaic energy systems are currently the world's most broadly employed renewable energy technologies. The efficiency of energy production using Crystalline Silicon technology has reached nearby 27%. As the inherent limitations of fixed PV panels result in suboptimal energy conversion, sun tracking technology may be addressed as a promising solution by dynamically adjusting the position of the solar panel to track the sun's movement. The photovoltaic panel is headed toward the sun to optimize the angle of incidence (the angle at which the sun hits a solar panel). A single-axis sun tracker tilts on a singular axis to follow the sun from east to west as it moves throughout the course of each day to increase the electric power and improve the poor efficiency of the photovoltaic panel.

This study compares different methods of solar position tracking systems using single-axis PV panels to quantify the increase in energy production versus fixed PV panels. A simple sun tracking method based on the sun-path diagram is compared with more advanced approaches using the incident angle of the sun ray, measured by a sun position sensor. Additionally, the electric output power of the photovoltaic system itself can serve as an indicator to track the sun's position with a commendable level of accuracy. Furthermore, during cloudy days when solar panel efficiency drops off by 10% to 25%, a hybrid sun tracker combining different types of algorithms may improve photovoltaic energy output. The study provides a better understanding of the effectiveness, benefits and limitations of the different single-axis sun tracking approaches.

2. TEST BENCH

A real-time embedded controller (CompactRIO of National Instruments) and a Web-based monitoring platform are developed to carry out this study (Moghaddam and Forestal, 2023). A test bench of 6 single-axis PV panels is used to facilitate the comparison of the different sun tracking methods, simultaneously under the same weather conditions. Measurements such as solar radiation, sun position in the sky, output voltage and current generated are considered to evaluate the different sun tracking methods.

As shown in Figure 1, the infrastructure used for the tests is composed of:

- A pool of 6 movable Single-axis PV panels fully equipped with different sensors such as sun position, output voltage, current, PV temperature as well as solar radiation.
- Two real-time embedded controllers of National Instruments with FPGA and CPU modules, IO modules and Ethernet connection allowing remote data monitoring. Each controller is connected to 3 PV panels.
- A common gateway interface with standard telecommunication protocols (WebSocket) for secure data transmission between the local infrastructure and the remote Web-based interface.
- A Web-based Interface offering an online monitoring panel which connects the users/programmers to the remote infrastructure. The Web interface proposes a user-friendly interface with live video streaming of the test site and data visualisation as well as different data logging features.

Figure 1: Infrastructure composed of movable single-axis PV panels, local controller, bidirectional data transfer and Web-based interface with remote monitoring tools.

3. SOLAR POSITION

In order to track the sun as the earth rotates, the sun's position in the sky by means of solar angles is needed. We start by defining the solar altitude, zenith and azimuth angles required for following the sun across the sky. Depending on the level of accuracy and complexity required, the solar angles can be calculated by using a variety of analytical, empirical or experimental methods. Once the sun's position in the sky is determined, it becomes crucial to calculate the optimal tilt angle of the PV panel. The tilt angle is determined to maximize the power output of the panel by ensuring the most efficient alignment with the sun's rays.

3.1. Solar angles definition

The solar angles refer to the position of the sun in the sky relative to a particular location on the Earth's surface. The solar angles are defined with two parameters: the azimuth angle and the altitude angle. The azimuth angle describes the horizontal position of the sun in the sky and changes throughout the day as the sun moves across the sky from east to west. The altitude angle describes the vertical position of the sun in the sky and changes throughout the day as the sun rises and sets, with a maximum angle at noon. Figure 2 shows that the azimuth and altitude angles can be used to calculate the direction in which the sun's rays are striking a particular location on the Earth's surface, which is important for determining the optimal orientation and the tilt angle for single-axis PV panels (Zhang *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 2: Solar angles.

3.2. Solar angles calculation

The solar angles can be calculated using a variety of methods, depending on the level of accuracy and complexity required. The three common methods are:

- Analytical methods: These methods employ mathematical equations to calculate the solar angles using inputs such as latitude, longitude, date, and time. The SPA (Solar Position Algorithm) is a widely used analytical method that provides accurate estimation of solar angles for any location on Earth. Other analytical methods include the NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory) Solar Position Algorithm and the ISES (International Solar Energy Society) Solar Radiation Data Manual.
- Empirical methods: These methods use statistical analysis of historical data to estimate the solar angles for a particular location. These methods are less accurate than analytical methods but can still provide useful estimates for practical applications. One example of an empirical method is the use of lookup tables based on historical solar radiation data.
- Experimental methods: Experimental methods use sensors or instruments to directly measure the solar angles in real time. For example, a sun tracker equipped with a photodiode sensor can be used to measure the azimuth and altitude angles of the sun and adjust the orientation of the solar panel accordingly.

In general, the most accurate method for calculating solar angles is an analytical method, but this requires access to accurate data on the location, date, and time. In this study, we use analytical methods for sun tracking based on open-loop strategy and experimental methods with real-time measurements for sun tracking based on closed-loop strategy.

3.3. Analytical method

We use several mathematical relations to reach an algorithm for finding the sun's azimuth and altitude angles before calculating the optimal tilt angle of the PV panel (Duffie and Beckman, 2013).

The zenith angle is an important solar angle used to describe the sun's position in the sky. It can be calculated by the following equation:

Equation 1: The zenith angle of the sun.
$$\cos \theta_z = \cos \varphi \cos \delta \cos \omega + \sin \varphi \sin \delta$$

Where:

- θ_z = Zenith angle of the sun (°)
- φ = Latitude of the PV location (°)

- δ = Angle of the declination (°)
- ω = Hour angle (°)

As for the angle of declination, it can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Equation 2: Angle of declination.} \quad \delta = 23.45^\circ \sin \left[\frac{2\pi(N-81)}{365} \right]$$

Where N is the day number defined as the number of days elapsed in a given year up to a particular date (e.g., the 2nd of February corresponds to 33).

The hour angle, ω , is the angular displacement of the Sun from the focal point and it is given by (Khatib and Elmenreich, 2016):

$$\text{Equation 3: Hour angle.} \quad \omega = 15^\circ (AST - 12h)$$

Where AST is apparent or true solar time and is given by the daily apparent motion of the true or observed sun. It is based on the apparent solar day, which is the interval between two successive returns of the sun to the local meridian. Apparent solar time is given by (Khatib and Elmenreich, 2016):

$$\text{Equation 4: Apparent solar time.} \quad AST = LMT + EoT \pm \frac{4^\circ}{LSMT-LOD}$$

The LMT is the local meridian time, LOD is the longitude, LSMT is the local standard meridian time, and EoT is the equation of time.

The LSMT is a reference meridian used for a particular time zone and is similar to the prime meridian, used for Greenwich Mean Time.

$$\text{Equation 5: Local standard meridian time.} \quad LSMT = 15^\circ (T_{GMT})$$

The EoT is the difference between apparent and mean solar times, both taken at a given longitude at the same real instant of time.

$$\text{Equation 6: Equation of time.} \quad EoT = 9.87 \sin(2B) - 7.53 \cos B - 1.5 \sin B$$

$$\text{Equation 7: Parameter B.} \quad B = \frac{2\pi(N-81)}{365}$$

The solar altitude angle (α_s) is the complement of the zenith angle:

$$\text{Equation 8: The solar altitude angle.} \quad \alpha_s = 90^\circ - \theta_z$$

Finally, the solar azimuth angle (γ_s) is equal to the angular displacement from south of the projection of beam radiation on the horizontal plane (Duffie and Beckman, 2013). It should be noted that the displacements east of south are negative and west of south are positive.

$$\text{Equation 9: The azimuth angle of the sun.} \quad \gamma_s = \text{sign}(\omega) \left| \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos \theta_z \sin \varphi - \sin \delta}{\sin \theta_z \cos \varphi} \right) \right|$$

After calculating the position of the sun in the sky with its altitude, zenith and azimuth angles, it is necessary to calculate the optimal tilt angle of the PV panel. The optimal tilt angle refers to the angle at which the panel should be tilted to maximize its power output. This angle is influenced by various factors, including the latitude of the location, the time of year, and the panel's orientation. The equation 10 is used to calculate the tilt angle based on the altitude and azimuth angles of the sun, as well as the observer's latitude.

$$\text{Equation 10: Tilt angle calculation of single-axis PV.} \quad \beta_{Tilt} = \tan^{-1}(\tan \theta_z |\cos(\gamma - \gamma_s)|)$$

Surface azimuth angle (γ) is the deviation of the projection on a horizontal plane of the normal to the surface from the local meridian, with zero due south, east negative, and west positive. The surface azimuth angle γ will be 180° or -180° depending on the sign of the solar azimuth angle:

Equation 11: Surface azimuth angle.

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} 180^\circ & \text{if } \gamma_s > 0 \\ -180^\circ & \text{if } \gamma_s \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

3.4. Experimental method

For experimental method, we use a sun sensor to measure the incident angle of the sun ray in orthogonal axes (Solar MEMS). The incidence angle of the sun ray in orthogonal axes is measured by a 4 quadrants photodetectors device. The sunlight is guided to the detector through a window above the sensor. Depending on the angle of incidence, the sunlight induces photocurrents in the four quadrants of the detector. Angle X and Angle Y specify the angular position of the incident sun ray inside the field of view of the chosen sun sensor, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Sun sensor based on a 4 quadrants photodetectors device and angles X and Y of the incident ray on the solar sensor.

Angles X and Y of the incident ray can be obtained with a simple set of equations involving the four photodiode voltages generated by the sun sensor. The accuracy of the sensor increases when receiving radiation perpendicular to the sensor, close to zero degrees in X and Y. This is an outstanding feature that makes it suitable for tracking applications.

4. SUN TRACKING STRATEGIES

This chapter presents the different sun tracking strategies by highlighting the advantages and limitations of each approach. A simple open-loop control strategy based on the sun-path diagram is compared to two different closed-loop strategies based on feedback measurements such as sun position and electrical power. The state of the art refers to many hybrid strategies combining different types of algorithms to show how the photovoltaic energy output can be boosted under different weather conditions (Gutierrez *et al.*, 2020), (Karafil, *et al.*, 2015). We propose a hybrid control using a switching mechanism based on the radiation level to switch between the different control strategies depending on the current weather conditions.

4.1. Open-loop control strategy

The open-loop control strategy for solar tracking relies on calculating the position of the sun in the sky described in chapter 3.3 to adjust the tilt angle of the single-axis PV panel. Two different methods have been implemented. The first method uses the equations 1 to 9 for calculating the position of the sun as well as the equations 10 and 11 for calculating the PV tilt angle. These equations can be simply implemented, for example as a bloc diagram in LabVIEW.

The second method uses the Ephem Python package (Rhodes, B.C., 2011) to calculate the sun's position in the sky, based on the date, time and location of the PV panel. Ephem is a powerful astronomy package that allows us to determine the precise position of celestial objects with high accuracy. Based on this library, a Python code has been developed to give the sun's position as a function of time and PV location. All the data saved in a database in CSV format is called in LabVIEW every 5 minutes to calculate the PV tilt angle setpoint, as shown in Figure 4. This method takes advantage of both LabVIEW and Python, allowing to exploit the easy-to-use LabVIEW graphical programming environment and the powerful mathematical and data processing capabilities of Python.

Figure 4: Bloc diagram for calculating the solar position via Ephem Python library and a Database.

Upon analyzing the database, we discovered that the sun's movement along its path within a duration of less than 5 minutes has a negligible impact on the tilt angle of the panels. Hence, a 5-minutes waiting time for each iteration has been defined as shown in the flowchart of Figure 5.

Figure 5: Flowchart for sun tracking based on open-loop control strategy.

4.2. Closed-loop control strategy based on solar sensor

A LabVIEW program has been developed to calculate the angles X and Y of the incident ray through the 4 quadrants photodetectors output signals. Considering the use of a horizontal single-axis PV panel and the requirement to track the sun's movement from west to east, only the Y angle was utilized. Through the sensor calibration process, the optimal Y angle of 15° was determined to achieve maximum output power at the PV panel location. As a result, an algorithm has been developed to calculate the optimal tilt angle to reach the maximum amount of power from the sunlight, as seen in the flowchart of Figure 6. Furthermore, the algorithm incorporates a 30-seconds waiting time for each iteration, which has been determined through extensive experimentation and analysis of the system's outputs and the time impact.

Figure 6: Flowchart for sun tracking based on a closed-loop control strategy with a solar sensor.

4.3. Closed-loop control strategy based on electrical power measurement

This method uses the electric output power produced by the photovoltaic system to track the sun's position with a good degree of accuracy. Figure 7 shows how the optimal tilt angle of the PV panel can be calculated in order to maximize its power output.

Figure 7: Flowchart for sun tracking based on electrical power measurement.

The algorithm starts by setting the actual measured electrical power of the PV panel as a reference. To begin calculating the optimal PV angle, 5 degrees are added to the actual PV angle. If the power of the PV panel increases compared to the previous power reference, it will be updated to the new value, and another 5 degrees are added to the PV angle. This process continues until the power reference becomes greater than the actual PV power. However, if the power of the PV panel does not increase in the first step, 5 degrees are subtracted from the PV angle, and the power is checked again. This iterative process continues by updating the power reference and subtracting 5 degrees from the PV angle until the power reference becomes greater than the actual PV power. Once the power reference exceeds the actual PV power, the algorithm

determines the optimal tilt angle setpoint and sends it for further action. In this algorithm, a 1-minute waiting time has been set through a series of experiments conducted under various conditions, considering the movement of the sun and the execution time requirement.

4.4. Hybrid control strategy

Hybrid control is a control strategy that combines two or more different control techniques to achieve better performance in a system. In a hybrid control system, the different control techniques are integrated in a coordinated way, taking advantage of each technique. The system switches between the different control techniques based on certain conditions or events to optimize the system's overall performance. Hybrid control is often used in complex systems where a single control strategy may not be sufficient to achieve the desired performance. In PV solar tracking systems, hybrid control can combine open-loop and closed-loop control strategies to maximize the amount of solar energy captured by the PV panel, for example by adapting possible changes in weather conditions and sun position.

In this section, we discuss the design and implementation of a hybrid control system for the solar tracking system that combines open-loop strategy described in chapter 4.1 and closed-loop control strategy described in chapter 4.2. The hybrid control system uses a switching mechanism based on the radiation level measured by a pyranometer to switch between the two control strategies depending on the current weather conditions. The hybrid control system is designed to operate in real time, to adjust continuously the orientation of the panel to maximize the amount of sunlight captured by the panel. Figure 8 shows the flowchart of the hybrid control strategy, combining the open-loop strategy and the closed-loop strategy using a sun sensor. The key element for switching decision is the amount of radiation (E_{solar}) which varies with the weather condition.

Figure 8: Flowchart of the hybrid controller using a pyranometer for switching mechanism.

5. EXPERIMENTATION RESULTS

The performance of the different sun tracking controllers described in chapter 4 has been evaluated based on the generated electrical power and has been compared with the power produced by a fixed inclined PV panel, without taking into account the energy consumption of the controller or the electrical motor. The fixed inclined PV panel was oriented to the geographical south with an optimum annual tilt. All the experiments have been conducted on the roof of the Campus "Energypolis" at University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland in Sion.

In Figure 9, the power generated by the fixed PV panel on a sunny day in May 2023 is compared to the power output of the PV sun tracker with an open-loop controller, as well as the PV sun tracker with closed-loop controllers based on a sun sensor and measured electrical power. During the experimentation time while the fixed PV panel showed an average power of 14.59W, the open-loop controller achieved an average output power of 16.35W, while the closed-loop controller based on measured electrical power reached an average output power of 16.77W and the closed-loop controller based on a sun sensor performed an average output power of 16.93W. These results indicate that the open-loop controller increased the output power by 12.06%. The closed-loop controllers, based on measured electrical power and sun sensor feedback, exhibited similar performance, increasing the output power by 14.94% and 16.03% respectively. Additionally, during the time interval from 10:51 am to 11:15 am, the angles of the three sun trackers closely matched that of the fixed panel, resulting in similar output power. Notably, at 10:03 am, there was a significant instantaneous increase in output power of up to 35.1% for the open-loop controller and up to 41% for the closed-loop controllers compared to the fixed panel.

Figure 9: Output Power of the PV sun trackers with different open-loop and closed-loop controllers.

Figure 10 shows the power generated by a hybrid control system during a partly cloudy day in May 2023. During the sunny time intervals, where a higher amount of radiation is recorded, the controller switched to closed-loop mode by using the sun sensor feedback. When the irradiation dropped with cloudy sky, the controller switched to open-loop mode to ensure the sun's path tracking. We have observed even when the cloud cover was thick and the sun sensor failed to detect the sun's rays, the controller could maintain the correct path. During the time interval "overlap of angle", the angle of the hybrid controller closely matched that of the fixed panel with similar output power. For the tests of Figure 10, the hybrid controller recorded an overall increase of 6% in average output power compared to the fixed panel.

Figure 10: Output Power of the PV sun tracker with hybrid controller switching between open-loop and closed-loop controllers.

6. CONCLUSION

The experimental results in this study demonstrate the significant benefits of implementing sun tracking control strategies in improving the performance of single-axis PV panel systems. Both open-loop and closed-loop control techniques proved to be effective in optimizing the output power of the PV panel compared to a fixed panel configuration, especially during the sunny days.

The hybrid control, combining the advantages of both open-loop and closed-loop control approaches, demonstrates its adaptability and improved performance, particularly during variable weather conditions. In fact, the hybrid control strategy provides better performance compared to either open-loop or closed-loop control separately. By combining the strengths of both control strategies, the system is adapted to different weather conditions and to changes in the sun's position more effectively for a better solar energy capture. In addition, the hybrid control strategy helps to increase the efficiency of the system by reducing the amount of energy required to track the sun. By switching between open-loop and closed-loop modes based on weather conditions, the system enhances the energy production when conditions are less favorable. In this way the hybrid system is more robust to weather disturbances and uncertainties.

Regarding the disadvantages of sun tracking control strategies, it is important to acknowledge the additional complexity they introduce to the system. Implementing sun tracking requires additional sensors, hardware, and advanced control algorithms, as well as the inclusion of switching mechanisms. This increases the cost of the system in design and development as well as in maintenance. Particularly, the hybrid control strategy requires careful design and testing to ensure that the switching mechanism works correctly with desired performance. Another drawback of the sun trackers is the energy consumption of the movable parts (motors and actuators) as well as the used sensors. For evaluating the output power performance of the sun trackers, we have neglected the energy consumption of the different elements.

Finally, these findings highlight the importance of sun tracking control strategies in maximizing the efficiency and output power of PV panel systems, making them a valuable consideration for solar energy applications. Further research and development in this field can lead to even more efficient control techniques, contributing to the widespread adoption and utilization of solar energy in various settings.

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